

Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka

wydanie specjalne

Warszawa

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(wydanie specjalne) Volume-2, № 5 October 2022

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Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka (HP) publishes outstanding educational research from a wide range of conceptual, theoretical, and empirical traditions. Diverse perspectives, critiques, and theories related to pedagogy – broadly conceptualized as intentional and political teaching and learning across many spaces, disciplines, and discourses – are welcome, from authors seeking a critical, international audience for their work. All manuscripts of sufficient complexity and rigor will be given full review. In particular, HP seeks to publish scholarship that is critical of oppressive systems and the ways in which traditional and/or “commonsensical” pedagogical practices function to reproduce oppressive conditions and outcomes. Scholarship focused on macro, micro and meso level educational phenomena are welcome. JoP encourages authors to analyse and create alternative spaces within which such phenomena impact on and influence pedagogical practice in many different ways, from classrooms to forms of public pedagogy, and the myriad spaces in between. Manuscripts should be written for a broad, diverse, international audience of either researchers and/or practitioners. Accepted manuscripts will be available free to the public through HPs open-access policies, as well as we planed to index our journal in Elsevier's Scopus indexing service, ERIC, and others.

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ESTABLISHING A CONTINUOUS SYSTEM OF IDENTIFYING TALENTED STUDENTS AND TRAINING HIGHLY QUALIFIED PERSONNEL

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Abstract: In this article, the issues of identification, selection and implementation of the system of work to be carried out for the training of qualified personnel of senior students in higher educational institutions are covered.

Keywords: management, creative, skilled, personnel, system, science, innovation, integration, composition, communicative, function, Business, Management.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада олий ўқув юртлирида иқтидорли талабаларни аниқлаш, танлаш ва малакали кадрлар тайёрлаш учун бажариладиган ишлар тизимини ташкил этиш ва амалга ошириш масалалари ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Иқтидорли, изходий, малакали, кадрлар, тизим, илм-фан, инновацион, интеграция, композция, коммуникатив, функция, бизнес, менежмент.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы организации и реализации системы выполняемых работ в высших учебных заведениях по выявлению, отбору одаренных студентов и подготовке квалифицированных кадров.

Ключевые слова: талантливый, творческий, квалифицированный, кадровый, системный, научный, инновационный, интеграционный, композиционный, коммуникативный, функциональный, деловой, управленческий.

Today , in order to achieve high results in the field of science, it is necessary to have deep knowledge in its various directions. It is impossible to achieve high goals in the field of science without effectively using the capabilities of modern computers and information technologies. In order to have the skills to use information technologies and their wide application in the fields of science, a perfect knowledge of foreign languages is required.

In order to deeply study the achievements of science and contribute to their further development, it is necessary for young people entering this field to have high abilities and opportunities, to choose a scientific direction in cooperation with highly qualified teachers, and to conduct their activities based on modern methodology, systems, technology and programs. .

The experience of our republic's educational system in attracting young people to the field of science on the basis of competition, targeting their desires, opportunities and abilities, organizing scientific activities on the basis of complex programs, and the weight of the achieved results is increasing. The programs and regulations for working

with talented young people have been developed in HEIs, and the established academies of talented youth are operating on the basis of the general regulations and programs approved by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. As a result, the number of young people achieving high results in science, culture, sports, modern technology, development of production and other fields is increasing day by day.

Scientific researches are being carried out in HEIs to create methods, systems and technologies to further improve the quality and efficiency of work in this regard.

The main goals of the research included the creation of a system and technology of events that would ensure that talented students would continuously and effectively engage in scientific activities during their undergraduate studies, achieve high performance on the subject of approved scientific work, and acquire the qualifications for independent scientific activity in the future. The analysis showed the need to conduct research on the improvement of organizations and methods of solving the following tasks in order to achieve the goals of the research.

1. Formation of dreams, wishes, ambitions and goals of young people to achieve high results in the field of science, assessment of their abilities and opportunities, and establishment of an effective system of application of targeted programs and methods.

To ensure that a talented student who wants to work in the field of science, before taking the first step in any direction of this field, has at least a little idea and understanding about the extent to which it is developing, the current problems that are waiting to be solved, and the need to perfectly master many aspects of this field in order to achieve high goals in the future. is of great importance.

2. Introduction of methods and technologies of scientific activity that ensure that young people achieve high results by working in the priority areas of science that are of great importance for humanity.

3. Improvement of measures to ensure that scientists and specialists acquire and put into practice modern methods and technologies of leading young people to the heights of science.

4. Effective use of the mentor-disciple method, which is known from history to lead to high achievements in the field of education and science, and introduction of modern systems and methods of training talented young scientists who are perfectly qualified to perform such a task.

5. Putting into practice the achievements of young people in the field of science, actively participating in the implementation of international grants and innovative projects, and improving and introducing methods and technologies for the formation of skills for effective operation based on the requirements of the market economy, etc.

In our country, consistent measures are being taken to support promising young people, to realize their talents, and to create additional conditions for effective scientific research and innovation activities.

At the same time, there is a need to identify talented young people and improve the continuous system of training highly qualified personnel in order to increase the enthusiasm

and intellectual potential of the growing young generation, as well as to increase the prestige of our country in the international arena.

It is necessary to turn young people into active participants in the ongoing reforms, to increase their motivation to learn science, to involve them in research and creativity, and to raise generations worthy of the ancestors who spread the fame of our homeland on a global scale. To do this, identify talented young people, support their activities scientifically and methodologically, popularize best practices and develop recommendations and manuals for educational institutions based on them. Organization of local and international, including non-state science olympiads among young people, ensuring their participation in international olympiads. Development of permanent new control materials for the Olympiads with the involvement of highly qualified specialists, highly qualified specialists of the participants of the international Olympiads. Including training involving scientists, professors, and foreign experts.

Integration of innovative corporate cooperation in higher education institutions of the Republic remains one of the most urgent issues. Today, education is becoming an important condition for introducing new technologies to all spheres of human activity, increasing competitiveness, and improving living standards. Taking into account the growing role of higher education in many countries, the strategy for its development is determined by national strategic priorities, and this strategy is aimed at improving the quality of higher education and expanding its access.

The beginning of market reforms in Uzbekistan, new conditions changed the structure of training of highly educated specialists, the demand for their knowledge and skills. Now there is a growing demand for personnel who can apply new knowledge in practice and understand the scope of innovative opportunities in a specific profession. These should be high-level specialists with analytical skills who can make the right decisions.

Currently, there are various problems in cooperation between OTM and employers. While higher education institutions consider their graduates to be knowledgeable, they often do not adequately meet the needs of employers. Many graduates have to work in another specialty or study in retraining courses. Based on this, it can be said that it remains an actual issue between OTM and a potential employer.

Integration of RTD, science and production - joint use of achievements and potentials in RTD, science and production. First of all, it is reflected in the training environment, training and retraining, and conducting joint scientific research. In practice, integration is understood as the joint work of several entities united for the same purpose. Integration, including different areas and levels, manifests compositional and communicative functions.

Function is the composition and structure of the integration, which unites the united subjects with informal and normative boundaries and their specializations.

Communicative function - represents the form and composition of inter-subject cooperatives, communication and mutual associations, adaptation of their principles and mechanisms to new conditions.

In today's development period, the "triple spiral" model of scientific production

interaction is widespread in the world (institutions of OTM production enterprise - institutes of the Academy of Sciences). academy of sciences - higher education - production enterprises.

OTM and enterprise cooperation:

1. Interest of the enterprise (permanent employment of qualified personnel, temporary employment of students for practical training, involvement of students in research and production, involvement of professors and teachers in scientific production and consulting, strengthening the position of the employer in the training of qualified specialists):

2. The interest of OTM (department) (participation in the employment of graduates, connecting specific course and diploma work with the problems of the enterprise, conducting employer monitoring in the training of specialists, providing students with a practice base, receiving orders in research and production, accepting enterprise workers for retraining)

3. Interest of the student (acquiring deep knowledge, qualification in a specific specialty, carrying out scientific work in a specific direction, motivation in a certain form, employment)

From the above system, the following factors affect the student's qualification:

1. The effect of general inter-university structures

2. The influence of the specialty department, including:

- The system of attracting junior students to majors;
- System of training students of the leading course;
- Influence of teachers;
- System of social application of students based on special educational technologies.

3. Influence of business and management representatives

4. The influence of parents

5. Influence of teachers

6. Internal rating of HEIs

At the current stage of development, a qualified student will have to develop a personality to work on. Because nowadays the requirements for employment are very high. A qualified student should have a guaranteed job in his specialty after graduation, and in the future, he should be a mature specialist in his specialty, competitive in all aspects, competent both academically and as a person.

It is necessary to study the problems of the enterprise at the higher education institution, and to give scientific topics for the qualification graduation work based on these problems.

The Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was created and approved by the Presidential Decree No. PF-58/47 of October 8, 2019. The following tasks are defined in this decree:

Establishment of mutually beneficial cooperation of education with production enterprises and scientific research institutes.

Practical implementation of five initiatives, which include comprehensive measures

aimed at creating additional conditions for the education of young students.

To ensure that higher education research students publish articles in prestigious international scientific journals with a high impact factor, increase the number of citations to articles, as well as ensure the gradual inclusion of republican scientific journals in the international scientific and technical base. At the same time, with this decree, the Concept of the development of the higher education system until 2030 and the "roadmap" for its implementation in 2019 were approved. Tasks to be implemented step by step are defined through this road map.

The concept envisages the following tasks:

- Creating a mechanism for selecting students for higher education institutions among talented young people;
- organization of scientific activities of higher education institutions based on the prospects of social and economic development of the regions, establishing innovative development forecasting activities based on analysis;
- Wide implementation of research results of innovative activities, commercialization of scientific developments, attracting talented young people to scientific research work, ensuring solid integration of education, science and production;
- Ensuring that scientific research works are focused on solving existing problems in the social sphere and economic sectors;

In addition, in this concept, among the strategic goals and priorities of the development of the higher education system, it is necessary to perform the following tasks;

- 1.Improving the quality of higher education training
- 2.Introducing digital technologies and modern methods to the educational process
- 3.Increasing the effectiveness of scientific research
- 4.Wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of innovative infrastructure of science
- 5.Increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work
- 6.Active involvement of personnel wholesalers in the process of training highly qualified specialists

The implementation of the tasks defined above is the result of the implementation of the Concept. In fulfilling these tasks, the structure of events held with talented students of each course can be defined as follows.

A system of activities with talented students studying in the 1rd year

- 1.1.To acquaint students closely with the achievements of science, modern techniques and technologies achieved in our country during the years of independence.

State programs planned to be implemented in our country in the development of priority areas such as economy, culture, science, technology, technology, industry, production, health care, ecology, effective use of natural resources, as well as launched industrial enterprises, organizing trips to large structures, cultural, health, sports and other fields of activity. As a result of the implementation of these activities, students get to know the achievements of our Republic in the years of Independence and the state

programs planned to be implemented, and their interest in effective work and creativity will increase.

1.2.To acquaint the students with the great contributions of our great scholars to the development of science in their time. Arranging discussions and seminars about the great contributions of our great scholars Al Beruni, Ibn Sina, Al Khorazmi, Amir-Temir, Alisher Navoi, Mirza Ulug'bek, Zahriddin Muhammed Babir and others to the development of science in their time, places named after them, historical organizing trips to places, museums, information resource centers and other places.As a result, students' knowledge about the contributions of our great ancestors to the development of science, their life and work, and their interest in working in the field of science will increase.

1.3.Familiarizing students with the Laws on education of our country, the structure and directions of education of the higher educational institution. Familiarizing students with the rights and obligations of young people, educational stages, official documents such as state educational standards, the history of the higher educational institution, existing educational directions, general activities and educational work organization structures, as defined by the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the fields of education and training.

Meetings with teachers - skilled pedagogues who have achieved high results in the organization of educational work, creation of educational literature and manuals, educational centers, laboratories and workshops. Organizing visits to information resource center, educational laboratory and workshops.

As a result, students learn to follow the rules and requirements set forth in the laws of our country, educational standards, and state educational standards.

They will have the opportunity to get to know the history of the educational institution, existing educational directions, system, rules and procedures for organizing general and educational work, available opportunities - information resource center, educational centers, laboratories and workshops, skilled pedagogues and their achievements.

1.4.To introduce students to the system of organization of scientific works of the Higher Education Institution and the directions of the scientific works performed . Introduction to the stages of education defined by the Laws of our country, directions of scientific work of Higher Education Institutions, history of their development, areas of current research, opportunities for carrying out scientific work, existing scientific center, departments and laboratories.

The implementation of such activities gives students the opportunity to get acquainted with the rights and obligations of those working in the field of science, as well as the opportunities of higher education institutions, and to gain an understanding of scientific activity.

1.5.To acquaint students with the main results achieved in the educational and scientific fields of Higher Education Institution.

Organization of talks and seminars about the life and work of scientists and specialists

who have achieved high results by working in the Academy of Sciences and fields of our Republic and in foreign countries in the areas of educational and scientific work of the Higher Education Institution.

Students get to know the lives and works of scientists and specialists of our Republic and foreign countries who have achieved high results in the fields of educational and scientific work of Higher Education Institution. They will have information about the relevance, scientific and practical importance of educational and scientific activities of higher education institutions, and their place in the field of science.

1.6.Targeted orientation of students who expressed a desire to do scientific work, taking into account their abilities and opportunities. Organization of meetings with leaders and leading specialists of enterprises where students can work after graduation, and organize trips to advanced enterprises, various educational and scientific centers.As a result, students will get information about the cooperation between the departments they are studying with the Republic scientists and enterprises, they will get to know the various enterprises they will work with in the future. Students will have a bank of information necessary for choosing a scientific direction, subject and teacher.

1.7.Assessing the abilities and opportunities of students who are continuously engaged in scientific work and wish to study at the next stages of education. Assess students' knowledge and presentation skills by testing their knowledge levels in informatics, computer literacy, information technology, and foreign languages, conducting interviews, and writing essays.

Interviewing the parents of students and determining their children's agreement to continue their studies and do scientific work in the future.

The results of such activities serve, first of all, for teachers to take into account their knowledge, abilities and opportunities when choosing a student, scientific direction and topic.

1.8.Creating opportunities for students to choose a scientific direction, topic and scientific supervisor. Organizing meetings and conversations of students with scientists who are planned to be appointed as their mentors, distributing abstracts of the scientific direction and topics proposed by the mentors. As a result, students choose a scientific direction, topic and mentor (s) based on their wishes, abilities and opportunities.

1.9.Creating plans and programs for effective performance of academic and scientific work of the student. The scientific leader (s) and the student jointly develop the program and calendar plan of the scientific and creative work to be carried out during the undergraduate studies and approve it in the established order. Scientific leader (s) and in the International Science Olympiads, hold meetings with the winners of the International Science Olympiads, develop programs and plans for participation in such Olympiads in collaboration with the scientific supervisor - the gifted student , and ensure their implementation.

2.3.Preparation of talented students to participate in contests of state grants to support young scientists of the Government of the Republic. To familiarize talented students

with the examples of grants allocated by the Government of the Republic to talented young people engaged in scientific work, the Regulations and requirements for participation in them, to hold meetings with young scientists who have such grants, to develop programs and plans for participating in grants in cooperation with teachers and students and to ensure their implementation .

2.4. Educating and preparing talented students to participate in grants from various international funds. Acquaint talented students with the requirements and rules for participation in grants of various international funds, hold meetings with young scientists who are holders of such grants, develop programs and plans for participation in grants, and ensure their implementation.

2.5. Training talented students to participate in exhibitions organized by the Government of the Republic, ministries, various foundations, joint ventures and organizations. Acquaint talented students with the procedures, requirements and rules of participation in exhibitions organized by the Government of the Republic, ministries, various foundations, joint enterprises and organizations, hold meetings with scientists and experts who participated in such exhibitions, develop programs and plans for participation in exhibitions and implement them provide an increase.

2.6. Training talented students to participate in exhibitions organized by international foundations, various companies and foreign countries . Acquaint talented students with the procedures, requirements and rules of participation in exhibitions organized by international foundations, various companies and foreign countries, hold meetings with scientists and experts who participated in such exhibitions, develop and implement programs and plans for participation in exhibitions.

2.7. To teach talented students to search for information about the latest advances in science and technology related to the topics of scientific work from mass media and organize their effective use. To teach talented students to use scientific, scientific-technical and reference journals, and to search for, sort and effectively use sources from the Internet where the latest achievements on scientific topics are published, to analyze and control the implementation of such work.

2.8. Teaching gifted students to create a database of their research topics based on news from various sources. To create their own data banks using scientific works, articles, conference materials, theses, patents, inventions, internet information, advertisements, exhibition materials, etc. organization of methodological assistance in the systematization of created banks.

2.9. To teach talented students to analyze and state the issues (scientific problems) seen in scientific sources, direction and relevance, novelty and purpose of the topic. To teach gifted students to compare several scientific literatures - the issue seen in the articles - setting the solved problems, the novelty, relevance and goals of the articles, and to place them continuously according to the sequence of development.

2.10. To teach gifted students to analyze and report the results and methods of solving problems (scientific problems) found in scientific sources. Talented students will have

the ability to solve problems found in sources related to their scientific direction and topics, and to express the results obtained orally and in writing, and to place them in a continuous sequence of development by comparing them.

2.11. Teaching gifted students to analyze and present the conclusions and recommendations of the work presented in scientific sources. Talented students acquire the skills of oral and written presentation of the conclusions and recommendations of works presented in the sources related to their scientific direction and topics, their continuous placement in the sequence of development.

2.12. Teaching talented students to analyze and describe the scientific and practical significance of the results obtained in scientific sources. Talented students acquire the skills of oral and written presentation of scientific and practical significance of the results presented in sources related to their scientific direction and topics, comparison and continuous placement in the sequence of development.

2.13. To teach talented students to fully study, analyze and report scientific works (scientific articles) in literature. To present to talented students the relevance, novelty, purpose, methods of solving problems, obtained results, scientific and practical significance of the work, the indicators of the scientific basis of the recommendations and conclusions, their comparison and the creation of a continuous sequence according to their various indicators. they will have the qualification.

2.14. Evaluation of scientific works conducted in the 2nd course with gifted students . With a gifted student , the head of the department (department) of scientific and methodical affairs of the Higher Education Institution, the department of organizing scientific research activities of gifted students , the work done in cooperation between faculty deans, heads of departments, group trainers and scientific supervisors is evaluated, the programs and plans of the talented student's work in the 3rd year are analyzed.

A system of activities with talented students studying in the 3rd year

3.1. Organization of scientific seminars for talented students who are studying for a bachelor's degree. Developing and approving the direction, work order and plan of the scientific seminars of the talented students studying in the bachelor's field of the scientific supervisors , organizing the presentation of exemplary lectures by talented young people - masters, doctors , etc. at the seminars. In this , it is determined that talented students will give an interim report about their research every 2-3 months, the main focus of the report will be the relevance, novelty, purpose of the work, methods of solving problems, the results obtained, their scientific and practical significance, and the conclusion. and focuses on sequential and comprehensive coverage of recommendations. Analysis and control over the implementation of the approved plan and set tasks is established.

3.2. Several supervisors are in the undergraduate course organizing general scientific seminars with talented students . Development and approval of the direction, work order, plans and schedules of general scientific seminars. Taking into account the exemplary lectures of masters, doctors, etc., and making sure that the lectures are as close as possible to the topics of scientific work of the seminar members.

3.3. Organizing the participation of talented students in scientific seminars and defenses of scientific works by talented young people. Organization of the participation of talented young people and professors in scientific seminars, defenses of graduation qualification works and master's theses, and meetings of Specialized Scientific Councils organized in the same directions at the Higher Education Institution.

Implementation of the above-mentioned activities will expand the scope of knowledge of talented students, increase their experience and skills in scientific lectures and scientific discussions.

3.4. Guiding talented students in the graduation qualification work of the bachelor's degree, approving work topics, developing and implementing work programs.

Development of plans and programs for completion of graduate qualification work, approval and control over their implementation.

Usually, it is appropriate that the head of the academic work of a talented student is appointed as the leader of the graduation qualification work, and the subject of the work is related to the direction and topic of the academic work of the talented student. Such a situation creates a great opportunity for talented students to continue their scientific activities.

3.5. To organize the completion of the graduation qualification work of the talented student within the specified time. To teach a talented student to analyze, compare and systematize the relevance, novelty and research objectives of the problems seen in the literature related to graduation work, methods of solving problems, the essence of the obtained solutions, their logical correctness, the reliability of the results, general conclusions and recommendations.

As a result of the event, a talented student acquires the skills of a complete analysis of scientific works, a continuous description of the results in a sequence of improvement, and a comparison of conclusions and recommendations.

Planning and providing methodological support for the analysis of literature relevant to the graduate qualification work of a talented student. Monitoring the completion of graduation qualification work based on the approved plan. Analysis of the solutions to the problems seen in the work, comparison with the existing solutions, assessment of the scientific and practical significance of the solutions, summarizing the recommendations and conclusions arising from the obtained solutions. Conducting review and discussion of graduation qualification work.

3.6. To teach a talented student to draw conclusions from the analysis of literature on the subject of his scientific work, to define the goals and tasks of the work. A talented student can draw general conclusions from the analysis of literature, define the goals and objectives of his scientific work research, and make a written statement of them. As a result, the goals and tasks of the scientific work that the talented student wants to perform are continuously connected with the results presented in the scientific literature, justifying, ensuring and stating their continuity. skills are formed.

3.7. To organize a talented student to justify and explain the relevance and news of

scientific work. To teach a talented student to justify and explain the relevance and novelty of the subject of his scientific work, and to organize the performance of the task.

3.8. Providing methodical and practical assistance to a talented student in determining the modern method(s) of solving the problem(s) seen in his scientific work. To organize a talented student to learn theoretical methods of solving the problem (s) set in his scientific work and to carry out research related to his topic. Determining the goals, tasks, and methods of conducting scientific experiments, as well as teaching experiments on the use of appropriate tools, creating appropriate opportunities for conducting experimental research.

As a result, a talented student acquires the skills of determining the methods of solving the problem (s) set in scientific work, conducting theoretical research, learning to use experimental research tools, and conducting experimental tests.

3.9. Teaching a gifted student to use the sizes included in state standards and various reference books. Teaching a talented student to use the requirements, definitions, rules, indicators, sizes and other values included in the state standards and international standards adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan and in various reference books. As a result of the events, talented students will have the skills to use state standards and various sources when necessary.

3.10. To organize the active participation of talented students in the competitions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and state scholarships of the Republic of Uzbekistan. To organize the active participation of talented students in internal competitions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and candidates for state scholarships of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3.11. Evaluation of the scientific activities of talented students during their studies in the 3rd course, development of conclusions and recommendations. The work carried out in collaboration with the talented students by the department (department) of scientific and methodical affairs of the Higher Education Institution, the head of the department for the organization of scientific research activities of talented students, faculty deans, department heads, group trainers and mentors was evaluated, and the scientific leader and the talented student in the 4th year were evaluated. programs and plans of the scientific works performed are analyzed.

1.4. A system of activities with talented students studying in the 4th year

4.1. Organizing the participation of talented students in international and republican competitions and exhibitions. Preparation of materials and organization of participation in International and Republican exhibitions based on the results of the scientific work being carried out. Among the selections, it is possible to include state grants and grants from international funds allocated by the Government of the Republic for the purpose of supporting talented young people.

4.2. Organizing participation of talented student in international and national scientific-practical conferences. Teaching a talented student to prepare and give a lecture based on the requirements of international and national scientific-practical conferences .

4.3. Teaching a talented student to prepare scientific articles, applications for state patents and copyright certificates. A talented student acquires the qualification of preparing scientific articles based on the results achieved, preparing applications for obtaining state patents and authorship certificates based on the Regulations of the State Patent Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

4.4. To organize the purposeful sending of a talented student to the internships in the curriculum. Taking into account the topic, programs and plans of a talented student when choosing the places of acquaintance, study, production and other internships specified in the curriculum.

Effectively using the opportunities available at the internship sites:

- teaching the methods and procedures of creating a data bank necessary for scientific work;

- definition of specific tasks;

- gathering, processing, summarizing data, drawing various patterns and conclusions;

- training to acquire the skills of effective use of the created data bank in scientific work.

4.5. Teaching the talented student to test and implement the results, conclusions and recommendations of the scientific work he has done in the appropriate place (enterprises). The results obtained from the scientific work of a talented student - various values, laws, conclusions and recommendations:

- comparison with the results presented in the scientific literature and comparative evaluation of the results;

- to test its adequacy using modern methods, equipment and facilities;

- place (enterprise) and - test in practical conditions;

- formation of skills for concluding contracts for the implementation of scientific work results with various offices and enterprises.

talented student the procedures and rules of participation in innovative projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign countries and international funds.

4.6. To teach a talented student the methods of evaluating the economic efficiency of the results of his scientific work. To teach a talented student the methods of evaluating the economic efficiency of the results of his scientific work by testing them in theory, experience and practice. Normative documents and theoretical methods based on science, which provide methods for assessing the economic efficiency of industry indicators related to the direction and topic of scientific work. Methods of evaluating production profitability used in enterprises, carrying out tests in modern techniques and technologies.

4.7. To teach a talented student the procedures and rules of participation in innovative projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign countries and international funds. Regulations for participation in grants allocated by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan to support innovative projects, current Law and regulations. Organization of participation in innovative projects of foreign countries and international funds based on procedures and requirements.

4.8.To teach a talented student to publish the results of his scientific work in prestigious magazines and Internet magazines of foreign countries. Teaching a talented student to prepare articles, theses, annotations and other materials based on the requirements of prestigious scientific magazines and Internet magazines of foreign countries.

4.9.Teaching a talented student to interact with leading scientists, specialists, creative (working) groups and to organize his own creative (working) groups in performing scientific work. To teach a talented student to interact with leading scientists, specialists and creative (working) groups in performing scientific work, and then to independently form creative (working) groups and work in cooperation with them.

4.10.To organize a gifted student to complete the graduation work of the bachelor's course. A gifted student's bachelor's degree graduation qualification work:

- summarizing the results and making a written statement;
- giving a full lecture;
- organization of internal and external discussions.

4.11.Preparation of a report on the scientific work of a talented student during his undergraduate studies. Organizing the analysis of the results achieved by the talented student in the scientific work, evaluating their scientific and practical significance, summarizing the conclusions and recommendations, and preparing the general report of the work.

4.12.Discussing the report of the completed scientific work. Obtaining reviews of scientists and experts on the report of the completed scientific work, conducting discussions of relevant departments and scientific seminars.

7. 4.13.To develop talented students ' feelings of national patriotism, to teach them to adhere to scientific ethics in the culture of communicating with scientists and experts, using literature, presenting their scientific work, holding discussions, reviewing scientific works, etc. To improve the quality of training of talented students in science, culture, technique, technology, industry, ecology, medicine and other priority directions of economic and social development of our country.

8.Introducing digital technologies and modern methods to the educational process

9.Increasing the effectiveness of scientific research

10.Wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of innovative infrastructure of science

11.Increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work

12.Active involvement of personnel wholesalers in the process of training highly qualified specialists

directing to achieve high results by carrying out scientific work in their fields. Forming the character of scientific ethics and adherence to requirements in conducting scientific negotiations, evaluating scientific works, drawing conclusions and recommendations.

4.14.Evaluation of the scientific activity of gifted students during their undergraduate studies.

To give a special assessment to the cooperation activities of the department (department)

of scientific-methodological affairs of OTM with gifted students, the head of the department of organization of scientific research activities of gifted students of OTM, faculty deans, heads of departments, group trainers. Evaluation of the results of scientific supervisor-talented student cooperation and the skills of scientific supervisors in training talented students.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of the implementation of the activities given for each course, the following actions will be carried out:

- 1.Improving the quality of higher education training.
- 2.Introducing digital technologies and modern methods to the educational process.
- 3.Increasing the effectiveness of scientific research
- 4.Wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, formation of innovative infrastructure of science.
- 5.Increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities.
- 6.Active involvement of personnel wholesalers in the process of training highly qualified specialists.

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On measures to identify talented young people and organize a continuous system of highly qualified personnel training. Tashkent, May 6, 2019.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. Tashkent, October 8, 2019.
3. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Tashkent, January 24, 2020.
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